

A SET OF VARIABLE NUMBER OF TANDEM REPEATS LOCI TO STUDY GENETIC DIVERSITY OF *X. FASTIDIOSA* POPULATIONS IN THE SALENTO PENINSULA

A. GIAMPETRUZZI¹, M. MONTES-BORREGO², P. SALDARELLI³, S. ESSAKHI³, M. SAPONARI³, B.B. LANDA^{2*}

¹DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE DEL SUOLO, DELLA PIANTA E DEGLI ALIMENTI (DISSPA) UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO, BARI, ITALY. ²CSIC INSTITUTO DE AGRICULTURA SOSTENIBLE, CORDOBA, SPAIN. ³CNR ISTITUTO PER LA PROTEZIONE SOSTENIBILE DELLE PIANTE (IPSP), SS BARI, ITALY.

***Corresponding author: blanca.landa@csic.es**

Extensive sampling of diseased olive trees and other infected hosts in the epidemic area of Apulia demonstrated the widespread presence of a single Multilocus Sequence Type (ST53) which is indicative that a single pathogen introduction led to the current outbreak in Salento. Fast-evolving VNTR (Variable Number of Tandem Repeats) loci were selected to study the genetic diversity of field populations since they have been previously shown to provide adequate resolution for *X. fastidiosa* populations in other crops. About 40 VNTR loci, previously described for *X. fastidiosa*, were searched for their presence in the CoDiRO draft genome. Of those, 14 VNTR loci were selected and tested against DNA samples from 20 *X. fastidiosa* isolates obtained from different crops and locations in Apulia. Amplifications and sequencing was performed to validate their usefulness. Results indicated that 3 VNTRs show no repeats in CoDiRo-type isolates, 1 VNTR has two different repeats, 3 VNTRs are no informative among Italian and other *pauca* isolates, and only 5 VNTRs show polymorphisms within Italian strains. Additionally, 26 new VNTRs were selected on the CoDiRO draft genome and new primer pairs designed. Those 26 VNTR loci are being validated by PCR amplification and fragment sequencing of different *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and the same collection of *X. fastidiosa* from the outbreak referred above. This set of VNTR loci can be used to study the genetic diversity of *X. fastidiosa* field populations in the Salento Peninsula, as well as the consequences of vector transmission of *X. fastidiosa* on the structure of these populations.